

Validity of the Theories of Excluded Volume Effect of Polymer Molecules in Dilute Solution as Applied to Some Cellulose Derivatives

BIBEKANANDA DAS and P. K. CHOWDHURY

Department of Applied Chemistry Calcutta University, Calcutta

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Applicability of recent theories on the excluded volume effect of polymer coils to solutions of three cellulose derivatives have been examined. The linear expansion factor α has been determined and the theories were tested in terms of the molecular weight dependence of functions of α . The α^3 -type relation was found to be nearest in agreement with experimental data.

RECENT developments in the theoretical aspects of the excluded volume effect of polymer molecules in solution have renewed the interest in studies of the dilute solution properties of high polymers. The classical approach to this problem is due to Flory and Fox^{1,2} who proposed the relation

$$\alpha^5 - \alpha^3 = 2\psi_1 C_M (1 - \theta/T) M^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where α is the linear expansion factor, θ is the familiar Flory theta temperature, ψ_1 is an entropy of dilution factor and C_M is defined as $-C_M = (27/2.5/2\pi^{3/2} \cdot N_A) (v^{-2}/V_1)(M/r_0^2)^{3/2}$, N_A being the Avogadro number, $\bar{v}$ & V_1 are the partial specific volume of the polymer and molar volume of the solvent, respectively. Two important modifications of eqn. (1) are due to Kurata-Stockmayer-Roig^{3,4} and Ptitsyn⁵. The Kurata-Stockmayer-Roig theory is based on an ellipsoidal model for the distribution of chain segments in place of the spherically symmetrical distribution assumed by Flory and Fox and relates the viscometric and statistical expansion factor as $\alpha_\eta^3 = \alpha_s^{2.43}$. They proposed the relation

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - \alpha^{\frac{1}{2}})(\alpha^2 + 1/3)^{3/2} \\ = (4/3)^{5/2} (3/2\pi)(\beta/a^3) N^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (2) \end{aligned}$$

between α and N , the number of chain segments, and claimed a better agreement with experimental data (β being the binary cluster integral and a the effective bond length). The theory proposed by Ptitsyn takes the interaction between chain segments into account and leads to an equation differing substantially from that of Flory and Fox. Taking into consideration the non-gaussian distribution functions for α , he derived the equation

$$[(4.68 \alpha^2 - 3.68)^{3/2} - 1] = C \cdot N^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots (3)$$

The purpose of the present communication is to examine the validity of these equations from the

expansion factor and molecular weight data for three cellulose derivatives, viz., Na-cellulose xanthate, Na-carboxymethyl cellulose and methyl cellulose in 1M NaOH, 0.5M NaCl and water respectively.

Treatment of experimental data :

The light-scattering and viscometric data obtained at this laboratory^{6,7}, are utilised to test the relationships (1) to (3). Viscometric expansion factors have been calculated according to the relationship $\alpha_\eta^3 = [\eta]/[\eta_\theta]$, the values being obtained from the equation $[\eta_\theta] = K \cdot M^{\frac{1}{2}}$. The K values were obtained from the intercept of $[\eta]^{2/3} M_w^{-1/3}$ Vs. $M_w^{1/3}$ plots, as suggested by Kurata *et al.*⁸ The data relevant to the present communication are summarised in Table 1.

Results and Discussion :

(1) Applicability of the Flory-Fox theory :

The Flory-Fox theory predicts that a plot of $\alpha^5 - \alpha^3$ Vs. $M^{\frac{1}{2}}$ should give a straight line passing through the origin. Fig. 1 shows the $\alpha^5 - \alpha^3$ Vs. $M^{\frac{1}{2}}$ plots for Na-cellulose xanthate, methyl cellulose and Na-carboxy methyl cellulose in their respective solvents.

Although good linearity of the $\alpha^5 - \alpha^3$ Vs. $M_w^{\frac{1}{2}}$ plot was obtained in the case of Na-cellulose xanthate (Fig. 1), the straight line instead of passing through the origin, gave an abscissa intercept corresponding to a molecular weight of 2.25×10^4 . With Na-carboxy methyl cellulose and Methyl cellulose, the deviation was even wider.

(2) Applicability of the theory of Kurata-Stockmayer and Roig :

Plots of $(1 - \alpha^{\frac{1}{2}})(\alpha^2 + 1/3)^{3/2}$ Vs. $M^{\frac{1}{2}}$ should be linear and should pass through the origin. Such a plot for Na-cellulose xanthate shown in Fig. 2, shows

TABLE I. LIGHT SCATTERING AND VISCOMETRIC DATA FOR THREE CELLULOSE DERIVATIVES IN THEIR RESPECTIVE SOLVENTS

Sample No.	$[\eta]_{(dl/g)}$	$M_w \times 10^{-6}$	α
(a) Sodium-cellulose xanthate in 1M NaOH			
S-1 F-1	6.6	1.35	1.28
F-2	2.6	0.33	1.17
F-3	1.5	0.14	1.12
S-11 F-1	5.1	0.91	1.24
F-2	3.5	0.53	1.20
F-3	2.9	0.39	1.18
(b) Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose in 0.5M NaCl			
S-1 F-1	8.4	2.18	1.18
F-2	3.6	0.59	1.11
F-3	2.8	0.40	1.08
S-11 F-1	4.5	0.77	1.14
F-2	2.1	0.25	1.07
F-3	1.6	0.17	1.04
(c) Methyl cellulose in water			
S-1 F-1	5.3	1.11	1.10
F-2	4.6	0.95	1.08
F-3	3.6	0.62	1.07
S-11 F-1	2.1	0.25	1.04
F-2	1.6	0.20	1.03
F-3	1.1	0.08	1.01

Fig. 2. Plot of $\left(1 - \frac{1}{\alpha^2}\right) \left(\alpha^2 + \frac{1}{2}\right)^{3/2}$ vs. $M_w^{1/2}$

according to K-S-R analysis for sodium carboxymethyl cellulose—●, sodium cellulose xanthate—○ & methyl cellulose—●

good linearity and passes through the origin as required. However, there was wide derivation from the theory with Na-carboxy methyl cellulose and with Methyl cellulose. Thus with the K-S-R theory,

Fig. 1. Plot of $\alpha^2 - \alpha^3$ vs. $M_w^{1/2}$ according to Flory Fox analysis for sodium carboxy methyl cellulose—● sodium cellulose xanthate—○ & methyl cellulose—●

although a better agreement with experimental data was reached, complete accord was not obtained.

(3) Applicability of the Ptitsyn theory :

According to the Ptitsyn theory, plots of $[(4.68\alpha^2 - 3.68)\alpha^2 - 1]$ Vs. $M_w^{1/2}$ are expected to give straight

lines passing through the origin. Fig. 3 shows the Ptitsyn plot for Na-carboxy methyl cellulose in 0.5M NaCl. In this case, a straight line passing through the origin was obtained. Good linearity was also shown by the plot for Na-cellulose xanthate in 1M NaOH (Fig. 3), the straight line passing through the origin, as required theoretically.

The experimental points for Methyl cellulose in water (Fig. 3), fall on a straight line, but the requirement of passing through the origin was not satisfied.

Fig. 3. Plot of $[(4.68\alpha^2 - 3.68)\alpha^2 - 1]$ vs. $M_w^{1/2}$

according to ptitsyn analysis for sodium carboxymethyl cellulose—●, sodium cellulose xanthate—○ & methyl cellulose—●

The results obtained indicate that of the three theories considered here, the α^3 -type relation proposed by Ptitsyn is the most successful in explaining the

experimentally observed solution behaviour of the three cellulose derivatives. Deviations from the behaviour predicted by the Flory theory is pronounced in all cases. This deviation which has been observed by others also,^{9,10} may be due to the inadequacy of the theory itself, or it may be due to the fact that α_η is not an unique function of z only, but depends also on the draining parameter. The results of the Monte Carlo calculations of Alexandrowicz¹¹ and Suzuki¹² indicate that there is a transition from the α^3 -type to the α^5 -type of relation with increase in N . Kato *et al*¹³ have observed that for α_η -values and at higher molecular weights (greater than 10^6) the α^5 -type seems to better represent the experimental behaviour. At molecular weights lesser than 10^6 , however, the α^3 -type shows better agreement. For cellulose derivatives, which have a high draining parameter, it is possible that the α^3 -type relation holds good upto a higher molecular weight range. Therefore, from the present data, it may only be said that in the molecular weight range studied and for viscometric expansion factor, the α^3 -type of rela-

tions seem to be better suited in explaining the solution behaviour of these derivatives.

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